

Methodology for Improving the Conceptual Basis of Effective Management of the Development of Small Industry Zones

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 4 Oct 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Nov 2024; **Published:** 25 Dec 2024

Abstract: It is of great importance to study the methodology of effective management of the development of small industrial zones. The article describes the methodology of improving the conceptual foundations of effective management of the development of small industrial zones, increasing competitiveness.

Keywords: small industrial zones, risks, principles of risk, investment performance, risk management, competitive environment.

Enter. "Methodology for improving the conceptual basis of effective management of the development of small industrial zones" is a very important and effective topic that illuminates the main processes for economic development. Research and practical measures aimed at strengthening the methodology and conceptual approaches for the development of small industrial zones and solving problems in their management will be carried out.

Research methodology.

As a research methodology, the risks, studying their group, were used such methods as observation, economic analysis, statistical grouping, comparative and systematic analysis.

The main part.

The methodology of effective management of the development of small industrial zones is a system of methods and practices aimed at developing small and medium-sized businesses and increasing the efficiency of production in this area. The main objective of this methodology is to ensure economically, socially and environmentally sustainable development in small industrial zones, while promoting local production, technological innovation and competitiveness.

The main principles of effective management of small industrial zones:

Increase competitiveness. In order to increase the competitiveness of enterprises in small industrial zones, it is necessary to standardize their products and services, introduce quality and innovative innovations.

Infrastructure development. Improvement of the infrastructure of small industrial zones - improvement of energy, transport, irrigation systems, information and communication technologies (ICT) and other important infrastructures.

Technical and technological updates. Openness to news, innovation and inclusion of new technologies. Such an approach helps improve small enterprises and increase efficiency in production.

Support through special programs and programs. Development and implementation of support programs for small industrial enterprises by the state and private sector, as well as training of qualified personnel.

Environmental efficiency. Practical measures aimed at providing small industrial zones with environmentally friendly technologies, preventing pollution and saving resources.

Steps of effective management methodology:

Analysis and monitoring. Analysis of economic activity in small industrial zones and evaluation of results through continuous monitoring.

Personnel and resource management. Personnel training, skill development and efficient use of labor force. Also, developing optimal methods of using resources.

Education and training. Improving professional training of persons working in small industrial zones, as well as ensuring their economic and social well-being.

Effective strategic planning. Development of strategic plans appropriate to the specific characteristics of each industrial zone. This will help them fully utilize their potential and increase their competitiveness.

Modernization of production. Equipping small industrial zones with modern technologies and modernizing production processes.

This methodology is aimed at improving production efficiency, developing local production and ensuring the competitiveness of small industrial zones.

The main conceptual frameworks and methodologies in the management and development of small industrial zones can be based on the following factors:

Strategic goals and objectives of industrial zones. Development and implementation of specific strategies for the development of zones. For this, it is necessary to take into account factors such as business environment, technologies and financial resources.

Infrastructure and logistics systems. Infrastructure, transport and communication systems are important for effective development of small industrial zones. Coordination of these systems plays a key role in creating favorable conditions for businesses.

Personnel training and skill development. In the development of modern industrial zones, the training of personnel and their involvement in work is an important task. This should be done to eliminate the lack of highly qualified personnel and specialists in production.

Economic efficiency and innovation. Use of high-tech innovations in small industrial zones, use of new production methods to increase economic efficiency.

Government and private sector cooperation. It is important to strengthen cooperation between the public and private sectors in the development of small industrial zones. Governmental support and regulatory measures should be developed.

Environmental and social sustainability. In the process of development of small industrial zones, it is important to maintain environmental stability and social balance. For this, it is necessary to develop and implement sustainable development strategies.

Methodologically, in this presentation, combining these factors, each element's interaction, coordination and their impact on development will be analyzed. Modern management systems, digitization, innovative technologies and marketing tactics play a key role in the

management of small industrial zones.

It is also important to develop individual approaches and methodologies that suit the characteristics of each small industrial zone.

Despite the fact that the number of SIZs established and operating in the republic is increasing day by day, a single scientifically based organizational and economic model of their establishment has not been developed. In our opinion, the main problems of the organization of small industrial zones include the following: lack of qualified personnel for industrial production in some regions, lack of initial funds for starting a business based on advanced foreign equipment and technology (this problem also applies to small business entities operating in small industrial zones), according to the level of socio-economic development of the regions, there is no scientifically based procedure for the placement of small industrial zones by regions, based on the division of small industrial zones into types, and the fact that a single system of criteria that takes into account their technical, ecological, economic and social aspects has not been developed in the selection of projects within small industrial zones.

Studying the experience of established and operating SIZs and foreign experiences, theoretically studying the existing problems, developing a unified model for the establishment and development of small industrial zones, preventing losses and finding solutions to the above problems to a certain extent.

Conclusions and suggestions:

In short, small industrial zones are an important source of economic development and job creation, and their effective management is important in ensuring the growth of the economy. a number of important methods and principles have been developed to effectively manage the development of small industrial zones. Effective management of the development of small industrial zones requires proper use of strategies, resources and innovation, as well as strengthening of legal and infrastructural conditions. All these factors together play an important role in the development of production activities and ensuring the sustainable growth of the economy.

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